

**USE OF MEDIA EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL
TRAINING OF FUTURE CIVIL ENGINEERS IN THE
INFORMATIONAL EDUCATIONAL
ENVIRONMENT**

Assistant. **Turgunov Mukhriddin,**

Namangan engineering - construction institute

Email. mturgunovmail@gmail.com.

Kokhorov Abdumonon

Namangan engineering - construction institute

Email. abdumannonqaxxarov@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

The purpose of this work is to study media education technology, media education research, its status in Uzbekistan and its application in trainings with builders-engineers in higher education institutions, and its impact on the development of professional training. learning is the analysis of the obtained results and implies application in future activities.

Keywords: *Media education, technology, educational technology, internet, information technology, education,*

The theoretical significance of the research is that it is enriched with theoretical approaches to the development of professional training of future builders-engineers through media education methods; The criteria and indicators for determining the level of professional training of future builders-engineers through media education methods, as well as the development of scientific and methodical recommendations that provide a positive solution to the research problem, the professional training of future builders-

engineers through media education methods It is explained by the improvement of the increase norms.

As a result of the research, the theoretical approaches, views, opinions and opinions on the mechanisms of increasing the professional training of future builders-engineers through media education methods are described with pedagogical and information technologies. Through media education methods, they will have scientific and methodological recommendations on the mechanisms of improving the professional training of future builders-engineers. In the research process, practical activities aimed at studying the actual situation of the problem, analyzing the available data, coming to certain conclusions, and evaluating the general situation based on the conclusions drawn have a special place. Conducting the preliminary experimental work on the basis of a specific project ensured the effectiveness of practical activities.

Based on the nature and content of the project, which is the theoretical basis, the following was implemented:

Organizational preparation stage. In this case, the objective and subjective factors implementing experimental work were determined:

- experimental areas were selected, which allow for starting experimental works;
- the number of teachers and students was determined as subjects of experimental work, they were divided into experimental and control groups based on random selection;
- the persons responsible for ensuring the consistency and coherence of the test work on the mechanisms of improving the professional training of future builders-engineers through media education methods were determined;
- preliminary designs for experimental work were prepared;
- based on the organization of surveys (questionnaires, tests, interviews), the level of professional training of future builders-engineers was determined through media education methods.

Experiment - test work was carried out in the following 3 stages:

1. Preparation stage.
2. Experience - the stage of direct organization of test works.

3. Final stage.

In the organization of experimental testing, the main attention was paid to the following:

1. Organization of pedagogical observation (determining the identity of the student and the content of educational activities).

2. To organize interviews in order to determine the state of theoretical and practical study of the problem.

3. Passing questionnaires and tests, questionnaires.

4. To determine the factors that shape the professional training of future builders-engineers through media education methods.

5. To study the sources of the problem and to have information about the factors related to them.

6. Further enrichment of research activities as a result of questionnaires and tests conducted with the participation of students. Experimental work was carried out at the Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute. 52 students were involved. Participants were conditionally divided into 2 groups. 1st experimental group, 2nd observational group. First, both groups were given the following questionnaire

Analysis of results. To question 1, 23 students said that they get information through the Internet, 20 students through television, and 9 students, newspapers and magazines. To question 2, 17 students said that they make a decision based on fashion, 25 students because of advertising through television and 10 students based on the information they received from their parents. To question 3, 32 students said they need the Internet, 15 students need television, and 5 students need newspapers and magazines. To question 4, 10 students said development, 7 students said news, 12 students said business, 10 online communication and 15 time saving.

As can be seen from the answers given:

35% of students understand well the role of mass media in their life.

30 percent of students know the role of mass media in their lives.

35% of students have a superficial opinion about the role of the media in their lives.

These results are as follows by gender:

The role of the media in his life	Boys (percentage)	Girls (in percent)
They understand the role of mass media in their lives.	44%	30%
They know the role of mass media in their life.	36%	40%
their opinions about the role of the media in their lives are superficial.	20%	30%

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